

MINISTRY OF FORESTRY
 FORESTRY RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT AGENCY
 CENTER FOR FOREST PRODUCTIVITY
 RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT
 IN COLLABORATION WITH
 NATIONAL WORKING GROUP ON INDONESIAN MEDICINAL PLANTS

International Seminar Proceedings

Forests & Medicinal Plants

for better human welfare

10–12 September 2013
 Bogor, Indonesia

International Seminar Proceedings
Forests & Medicinal Plants
 for better human welfare

Ministry of Forestry
 Forestry Research and Development Agency

**Centre For Forest Productivity
 Research and Development**

Jl. Gunung Batu No. 5, Bogor Po. Box 331
 Phone (0251) 8631238 Fax. (0251) 7520005
 E-mail: pp_p3ht@yahoo.co.id, pusprohut@gmail.com
 Website: www.forplan.or.id

International Seminar Proceedings
Forests & Medicinal Plants for Better Human Welfare

10-12 September 2013

Bogor, Indonesia

© 2014 by Center for Forest Productivity Research and Development

Editors:

Dr. Ir. Molide Rizal, MSc, Ir. Nunuk M. Januawati, MS, APU, Ir. Yuli Widyastuti, MP, Prof. Dr. L. Brotokardono, Drs. Riskan Effendi, MSc, Dr. Ir. Dede Rohadi, MSc, Dr. Tuti Herwati, S.Hut, MSi

International Seminar Forests & Medicinal Plants for Better Human Welfare
10-12 September 2013. Bogor, Indonesia. Center for Forest Productivity
Research and Development, Bogor, Indonesia.

Published by:

Center for Forest Productivity Research and Development
Jl. Gunung Batu No. 5, Bogor Po. Box 331
Phone (0251) 8631238 Fax. (0251) 7520005
E-mail: pp_p3ht@yahoo.co.id, pusprohut@gmail.com
website: www.forplan.or.id

ISBN : 978-979-3819-87-7

Cover Design : Bintoro, S.Kom

Printed in Indonesia

THE POTENCY OF FALOAK'S (*Sterculia quadrifida*, R.Br.) ACTIVE COMPOUNDS AS NATURAL REMEDY

Siswadi, HenyRianawati, Grace S. Saragih and Dani S. Hadi

Forestry Research Unit Kupang
Jl. Untung Surapati No. 7 Kupang, Nusa Tenggara Timur, Indonesia
Phone. (+62-380) 823357, Fax. (+62-380) 831068
Email: ady_plk@yahoo.com

ABSTRACT

East Nusa Tenggara (NTT) province is semi arid region with low precipitation and its vegetative cover is characterized mainly by shrubs, scrubs, and grass. However, there are some useful plant that can be found in this province. People on Timor island use Faloak (*Sterculia quadrifida* R.Br. 1844) bark as herbal remedy to cure diseases such as liver diseases, gastroenteritis and as stamina booster. In order to identify active compounds in Faloak bark, analysis was done in The Integrated Research and Testing Laboratory, Gadjah Mada University. Extracts obtained from maceration method using four solvents; aseton, n-hexane, diethyl ether and ethyl acetate. Extractions using 20 gram of Faloak bark, 3 times replication and produce approximately 47.53% active compounds. The extraction shows the presence of alkaloid, flavonoid, terpenoid and phenol, but saponin was not detected. These active compounds in Faloak bark were known as antihypertensive, antimalarial, anticancer, antimicrobial, antioxidant, and antiseptic. Therefore, faloak is potential herbal remedy to cure bacterial diseases, gastroenteritis, hypertension and liver diseases.

Keywords: Herbal, active compounds, *Sterculia quadrifida*.

I. INTRODUCTION

The World Health Organization (WHO) estimates that about 80% people of the world who live in rural areas still depend on medicinal plants to maintain their health (Anonymous, 2001). Role of plants for traditional societies almost cannot be replaced by modern chemical drugs (Hidayat, 2007). Ong (2000) said that the Indonesian nation has long been familiar with the efficacy of a wide variety of plant species as a means of health care, treatment and to beautify themselves which is known as *Jamu*. Among international societies, *Jamu* known as "herbs" is derived from the Latin word meaning grass, stalks, soft green small stalks and leafy bit.

One type of plant that is used for traditional medicine is faloak (*Sterculia quadrifida*). Faloak is a species with a lot of benefits but the research of faloak is mealy. Nowadays Forestry Research Institute of Kupang start examining the content of the active compounds contained in them.

The purpose of this study was to determine the active compounds of faloak bark and benefits of them for humans health.

II. METHODOLOGY

Faloak bark samples were taken in the city of Kupang on growing altitude 200 masl and analyzed in July to August 2012.

A. Retrieval Simplisia

Faloak bark samples taken manually by peeling the bark of mature trees faloak which diameter 35 cm. The bark of faloak which obtained in size 10 x 25 cm be dried at room temperature until the sample analysis is done.

B. Sample Analysis

In order to identify active compounds in Faloak bark, analysis was done in The Integrated Research and Testing Laboratory, Gadjah Mada University. Extracts obtained from maceration method using four solvents; acetone, n-hexane, diethyl ether, and ethyl acetate.

Extraction of the faloak bark is maceration extraction. The steps are: Faloak bark is cut, dried at temperature 54°C for 48 hours and then made of powder with sieve which it diameter 1 mm. The work step is in Figure 1.

Figure1. Flow chart of faloak bark extraction

C. Phytochemical Test

Phytochemical test was conducted to determine bioactive components what present in the test sample so that it is expected to be used in accordance with its function and benefits. Phytochemicals analyses are a common method used to detect the presence of secondary metabolites present in plants. The main compounds contained in plants have several types that can be detected by following the Harborn method (1987). While testing done qualitatively with the aim to identify the main compounds in the faloak bark include alkaloid, flavonoids, saponins, phenolic and terpenoids.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Making Extract

Maceration derived from the Latin "macerare" which means soaking. Extracting simplicia/vegetable material made by soaking the material using a solvent instead of water (nonpolar solvent) or half water, over a period of time in accordance with the rules in the official books of pharmacy (Indonesian Pharmacopoeia, 1995).

Faloak bark extraction process begins with drying simplisia followed by making simplisia into powder. Results obtained from this process that the dry raw material weighing 399.160 grams after milled and sieved using a sieve diameter 1 mm produces 383.450 grams which means it is in the process there is 4% gram of raw materials are lost. The result of faloak bark extraction at Table 1.

Table 1. Data of faloak (*S. quadrifida*) bark extraction

Weight of faloak bark (wet)	Weight of faloak bark (dry)	Drying shrinkage
20 gram	9.870 gram	49.35%
20 gram	9.220 gram	46.10%
20 gram	9.430 gram	47.15%
Average		47.53%

Source: Laboratory Test Results in 2012

Drying process at a temperature of 45 °C for 48 hours produces raw materials simplisia as much as 47.53 %, this illustrates that the water content contained in the raw material simplisia bark of faloak as much as 52.47 %. The extraction of simplisia faloak shown in Table 2.

Table 2. The effect of fraction with the number of faloak bark extracts

Fraction (solvent)	Weigh of the powder bark (gram)	Weight of the resulting extract (mg)	Percentage of extract (%)
Acetone	25	1,730	6.92
n Hexane	25	100	0.4
Diethyl eter	25	273	1.09
Ethyl acetate	25	110	0.44
Ethanol 96%	25	1,970	7.88
Water	25	1,170	4.68

Source: Laboratory Test Results in 2012

Every type of fractions produces the amount of extract different. In the extraction process, the solvent used is a solvent that has a high dissolving power toward the substances which extracted. High dissolving power correlate with the polar solvent and polar compounds which extracted. There is a strong tendency for polar compounds soluble in polar solvents, and vice versa. This principle is called "like dissolves like". Acetone classified into standard solvent extraction components to extract timber recommended by the CPPA and ISO for testing related to TAPPI test method, because acetone can be extract polar compounds, semi-polar and non-polar (Stenius *in* Ranta, 2011).

The use of some types of fractions in faloak bark extraction process aims to get the best type of solvent that can be used to extract crude drug which analyzed. This is very important because the nature of each different simplisia. The extraction results illustrate that the fraction of acetone and 96 % ethanol is the best type of fraction for extracting of faloak bark are 1,730 mg and 1,970 mg or by 7.88 % and 6.92 %. However use Hexane and n Etheil acetate extracts only able to produce as much as 100 and 110 mg per 25 gram of powder simplisia faloak or 0.4 %.

B. Phytochemical Test

Phytochemicals in its broadest sense is any kind of chemicals or nutrients derived from plant sources, including fruits and vegetables. In common usage, phytochemical has a narrower definition. Phytochemicals are usually used to refer to compounds found in plants that are not needed for normal body functions, but it has a beneficial effect on health or an active role for the prevention of disease. Therefore, these substances different from what is termed as a nutrient in the traditional sense, is that they are not a necessity for normal metabolism and the absence of these substances will not result in deficiency disease in which normal period for such deficiency.

According Hartanto *in* Simbala (2009) in plant tissue, there are two systems, namely primary and secondary metabolism. Primary metabolism is processing of proteins, lipids, carbohydrates and nucleic acids. Whereas secondary metabolic processes produce phenol compounds and phenol acids, terpenoids, flavonoids, phenolic saponins, tannins and class of nitrogen compounds such as alkaloids. The phytochemical test results bark faloak presented in Table 3.

Table 3. The Phytochemical test results bark faloak

Name of the test compound	Qualitative chemical analysis			
	Aceton extract	Eter extract	Etilasetat extract	Heksan extract
Alkaloid	Negative	Positive	Positive	Positive
Flavonoid	Positive	Positive	Positive	Positive
Saponin	Negative	Negative	Negative	Negative
Phenolic	Positive	Positive	Positive	Negative
Terpenoid	Positive	Positive	Positive	Positive

Source: Laboratory Test Results in 2012

Compound detection analysis results in Table 3, shows that the flavonoids and terpenoids can be detected using all kinds of fractions. However, saponin compounds are not detected by the four types of fractions. Phytochemical test is very useful for determining the principal classes of active compounds extractive substances bark of faloak that have characteristic antimicrobial. Here are some of the benefits of an active compound found in the faloak bark.

1. Alkaloid

In the medical world and organic chemistry, alkaloid has long been an important and integral part in the research of experts, which the alkaloid is an organic compound largest found in nature. Almost all alkaloids derived from plants and are widespread in many plant species. In addition to leaves, alkaloid compounds can be found in the roots, seeds, twigs, and bark. By organoleptic, foliage "sepat" and bitter taste, usually identified containing alkaloids. Alkaloid have a trigger effect on the health of nerves, increase blood pressure, reduce pain, antimicrobial, sedative, medication for heart disease and else (Robinson, 1995). Results of research conducted by Simbala (2009), the 45 species of medicinal plants used by people in Minahasa regency, 97.83 % among them positive discovered alkaloid.

"Sepat" flavors that appear in the result of the water decoction of the faloak bark is possibility generated by alkaloid compounds. Alkaloids in the faloak bark can be detected with ether fraction, ethyl acetate and hexane but not detectable with acetone fraction.

2. Flafonoid

Flavonoid is the largest class of phenolic compounds (Nurmillah, 2009). For the plants, flavonoids function for plant growth regulators, giving color, protecting from ultra violet, photosynthesis regulator, antimicrobial and viruses. While for humans flavonoids can be used as an antibiotic against cancer and kidney, inhibits bleeding, antioxidants, controlling free radicals, reduce blood clotting and for the recovery of dead/damaged cells in the liver.

Indeed unwitting people in the East Nusa Tenggara province have utilized flavonoid compounds in the treatment of hepatitis and liver disease. In the world of herbal health, flavonoids developed to prevent or treatment of diseases associated with free radicals (Birt *et al.*, 2001). As we know that the majority of free radicals

enter the body from the external environment such as from cigarette smoke, alcohol consumption, electromagnetic radiation, through exposure to sunlight, consumption of junk foods, air pollution, etc.. Even stress can produce high levels of free radicals in the body. Interview results are known from a few cases recounted by former patients with hepatitis A, hepatitis B and liver disease which we encountered that the cause of the disease stems from irregular diet, lack of rest and excessive consumption of alcoholic beverages. Flafonoid on faloaksimplisia can be detected by all factions including acetone fraction.

3. Phenolic

Phenolic compounds, as Table 3 can be detected with all factions, except hexane. Phenolic acid is an essential element of polyphenols and are found abundant in fruits and vegetables. According Wrsiati *et al.* (2011) phenol are group of chemical compounds that can be found in plants. These compounds are characterized by the phenol group that played a role in plant color like the color of leaves in autumn. In line with this, the faloak tree is a plant with characteristics shed leaves during the formation of generative which generally lasts from June to September. The Faloak leaves which green color, looks more green at the time of its inception after the coming of spring. Phenolic acids are simple molecules that are easily absorbed in the human metabolic system because it is easily soluble in water (Harborne, 1987) and offers a variety of anti-aging benefits. (Meskin *et al.* Within Nurmillah, 2009) the structure of phenolic compounds has antioxidant and antitumor effects.

4. Terpenoid

Presence of terpenoid compounds in the faloak bark can be detected using the four fractions, as shown in Table 3. Terpenoids are formed from aisonapra and for plants function in protection against insects. One class of terpenoids that act as anti-microbial is triterpenoids are widely used to cure skin disorders, antifugus, insecticide, antibacterial and antiviral. Triterpenoids least be selected into four groups, among others triterpana, steroids, glycosides and saponins (Robinson, 1995). Analysis for faloak bark by using all kinds of factions did not detect the presence of saponin compounds. According to Arcuri P.B. (2004) saponins may reduce the antherosceloris risk due to its ability to bind cholesterol.

This study is an initial step to determine the content of the active compounds in the faloak bark and its correlation with the use who done by the people in East Nusa Tenggara. From the results of the qualitative test is still required testing and other studies such as quantitative test, classifying compounds more detail, compound isolation and usage techniques that are safe for human.

IV. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATION

A. Conclusions

1. Shrinkage caused by water loss from the faloak bark at the drying process is equal to 52.47 %,

2. Eethanol 96% and Aceton fractions produce the most many extracts the faloak bark.
3. Flovonoid, and Terpenoids can be extracted using four types of solvents (Aceton, Ether, Ethyl acetate, Hexane), while saponin was not found in the faloak bark.

B. Recommendation

In order to get better benefits, need for more specific studies related derivative/class from compounds which discovered and isolation techniques.

REFERENCES

- Arcuri, P.B. 2004. <http://www.ansci.cornel.edu/cources/ac625/625pholyphytox.html>. Accesed on 2 Agustus 2013.
- Bapedal & Fakultas Kehutanan IPB. 2001. *Rancangan strategi konservasi tumbuhan obat Indonesia*. Kerjasama Pusat Pengendalian Kerusakan Keanekaragaman Hayati, BAPEDAL & Fakultas Kehutanan IPB. Bogor.
- Birt, D.F., S. Hendrich, W. Wang. 2001. Dietary agents in cancer prevention: Flavonoids and Isoflavonoids. *Pharmacology and Therapeutics. E Journal, Elsevier*.
- Hidayat, S. 2007. Pengamatan keberadaan tumbuhan obat langka di Taman Nasional Ujung Kulon. *Buletin Kebun Raya Indonesia*.
- Harborne, J.B. 1987. *Metoda fitokimia*. Institut Teknologi Bandung. Bandung.
- Nurmilla, O.Y. 2009. *Kajian aktifitas antioksidan dan antimikroba ekstrak biji, kulit, buah, batang dan daun tanaman jarak pagar (Jatropacurcas sp.)*. Fakultas Teknologi Pertanian IPB. Bogor.
- Ong, C. 2000. Prospek industri obat asli Indonesia. *Seminar "Tumbuhan Obat di Indonesia"*, Kerjasama Indonesian Resource Centre for Indigenous Knowledge (INRIK), Universitas Pajajaran dan Yayasan Ciungwanara dengan Yayasan KEHATI.
- Robinson, T. 1995. *Kandungan organik tumbuhan tinggi*. Penerjemah: Kosasih Padmawinata. Institut Teknologi Bandung. Bandung.
- Simbala, H.E.I. 2009. Analisis senyawa alkaloid berberapa jenis tumbuhan obat Ssebagai bahan aktif fitofarmaka. *Pacific Journal*. Sumatra Utara. Medan.
- Ranta, F. 2011. Sifat antimikroba zat ekstraktif pohon faloak (*Sterculia comosa* Willich).
- Wrasiati. L.P., A. Hartati, D.A.A. Yuarini. 2011. Kandungan senyawa bioaktif dan karakteristik sensoris ekstrak simplisia bunga kamboja (*Plumeria sp.*) *Jurnal Biologi XV (2)*. Universitas Udayana. Denpasar.